

Kinetics and Mechanism of Base Hydrolysis of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-methoxybenzoatopentaamminecobalt(III) Complexes

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The kinetics and mechanism of the base hydrolysis of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-methoxybenzoatopentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorates have been investigated spectrophotometrically in the temperature range 35 to 50° and at ionic strength 0.3 *M* (NaClO₄). The reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions which obeyed the rate law

$$k_{obs} = k_1[\text{OH}^-]$$

The rate and activation parameters have been computed.

INTRAMOLECULAR attack of a nucleophile at a suitably situated electrophilic centre of the molecule is an established fact in certain organic reactions¹⁻³. This type of interaction in the base hydrolysis of suitable carboxylatopentaamminecobalt(III) systems has been of considerable interest in recent years^{4,5}. In a previous communication from this Laboratory⁶, in the base hydrolysis of salicylatopentaamminecobalt(III) ion, intramolecular attack of the phenate group at the cobalt(III) centre leading to Co—O bond fission has been postulated. In the present investigation, the base hydrolysis of *o*-methoxybenzoatopentaamminecobalt(III) complex has been studied in order to examine the possibility of the methoxy oxygen attacking at the Co(III) centre in a manner similar to the salicylato complex. For comparison, base hydrolysis of *m*- and *p*-methoxybenzoatocobalt(III) ions have also been undertaken.

Experimental

Aquopentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorate was prepared and purified by the method of Splinter, Harris and Tobias⁷. *o*-Methoxy-, *m*-methoxy- and *p*-methoxybenzoatopentaamminecobalt(III) perchlorates were prepared from the aquopentaammine complex and the corresponding anisic acids as described by Gould and Taube⁸ and were purified by repeated crystallisation from aqueous perchloric acid solution and dried over fused calcium chloride at room temperature. The purity of the complexes were checked by estimating for cobalt⁹. Analysis: Calcd. for [RCo(NH₃)₅](ClO₄)₂ (where R=C₆H₄(OCH₃)CO-O): Co, 11.9%; found for, R=*o*-methoxybenzoate, Co, 11.60%; R=*m*-methoxybenzoate, Co, 11.63% and R=*p*-methoxybenzoate, Co, 11.56%.

For spectrophotometric measurements, the anisic acids were recrystallised twice from water and dried

at room temperature. Reagent grade sodium perchlorate was used to adjust the ionic strength. All other chemicals were of reagent grade. All the solutions were prepared in distilled water. A Beckmann DU2 spectrophotometer was used for optical density measurements using 1 cm matched quartz cells. The method of following the kinetics is exactly similar to one already reported⁶.

Results and Discussion

The alkaline hydrolysis of the *o*-, *m*- and *p*-methoxybenzoato complexes was studied under pseudo-first order conditions. In the alkali range studied, the rate of the reaction was found to be first order in [OH⁻]. The kinetic results fitted best to the rate law

$$-d\ln[\text{complex}]_{\text{total}}/dt = k_{obs} = k_1[\text{OH}^-] \dots (1)$$

k_{obs} (observed pseudo-first order rate constant), k_1 and the activation parameters (ΔH^* and ΔS^* for the k_1 -path) and their error limits were calculated by means of least square computer programme as reported in literature⁹. The activation parameters were calculated from the transition state equation

$$k_1 = \left(\frac{RT}{Nh} \right) \exp(-\Delta H^*/RT + \Delta S^*/R)$$

Table 1 presents the values of ' k_{obs} ' at different alkali concentration and the corresponding values of ' k_{cal} ', ' k_{cal} ' being the product of the best value of ' k_1 ' and [OH⁻]. The values of ' k_1 ' at various temperatures are also collected in Table 1 while the activation parameters for the three complexes are collected in Table 2. The activation parameters for the base hydrolysis reaction of several other carboxylatopentaamminecobalt(III) systems which have been reported are also collected in Table 2 for the sake of comparison.

changes in ΔS^* , the values of which presumably suggest that solvation at the carboxyl group of the outgoing ligand depends strongly on the electrostatic field effect of the OMe substituent. Since the field effect will assist the solvation of the carboxyl group through hydrogen bonding it is quite natural that ΔS^* decreases as $o\text{-OMe} < m\text{-OMe} < p\text{-OMe}$.

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